

The Effect of Manpower Planning on the Performance of Employees: A Case Study of Manufacturing Industry of DELHI/NCR

Rashi Srivastav

Research Scholar, K.R. Mangalam University, Gurugram

Dr. Richa Arora

Assistant Professor, K.R. Mangalam University, Gurugram

Corresponding Email: rashi1994srivastav@gmail.com

Received: 07th January 2021

Revised: 21st march 2021

Accepted: 15th April 2021

Abstract: This research focuses on effect of manpower planning on employee's performance who is working in medical device manufacturing industries in DELHI/NCR. The purpose of this research is to know the impact of manpower planning on employee's performance and to determine the factors which affect the performance at workplace. For our research we have chosen the eight medical device equipment manufacturing industries of DELHI/NCR. Primary data has been collected through questionnaires. We have collected the response from two levels: managerial and non-managerial personnel's. We received 506 response through questionnaires from non-managerial personnel's and 46 responses through questionnaires from managerial personnel's. It can be concluded from the findings that the employees of an organization have proper understanding towards the attainment of the goals of an organization. The organisation should take special steps to improve the physical ambience emphasising on adequate workspace, proper lighting and noise management. It is revealed from the test results that there seems to be a significant difference between the employee productivity and extrinsic variables, and there exists a correlation between extrinsic variables and employee performance. So, the organisation should take necessary and adequate steps to improve upon factors like technical supervision, interpersonal relations, salary and working conditions. There also exists a correlation between the intrinsic variables and employee performance. Moreover, the findings also reveal that physical components and behavioural components does not have any relationship with performance of the employees.

Keywords: Manpower planning, employee's performance, organizational effectiveness, manufacturing industry

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Manpower planning and Development

Manpower planning and development is the first and the most significant function of management. The embodiment of manpower planning and development includes a basic examination of the inventory, demand, excess, shortage of resource and use of HR. Note that manpower planning is regularly taken as the main assets of an organization on the grounds that through it, different assets (material and monetary) are saddled to address the issue of labors. The economic development of a nation relies upon the quality and amount of its assets, the condition of innovation and productive organization of assets in both creation and utilization process. Most organizations today is dealing with issues since they didn't design for their labor force neither do they have any orderly HR the executives programs that think about hierarchical objectives. Planning is the first and most significant capacity of the board. The pith is to plan for and foresee future occasions. Planning goes past endeavoring to achieve expressed hierarchical destinations. It includes the advancement of methodology and strategies needed for compelling acknowledgment of the entire plan.

1.2 Manpower Planning in Manufacturing Industry

Manpower planning includes choosing missions and accomplishing them, it requires dynamic that is browsed among elective future reasons for activity. Manpower planning provides the opportunity to achieve organizational goals.

Berneth (1996) characterizes Manpower planning as the purposeful and precise assurance of future to satisfy the organization's main goal and meet its targets, give specific anticipated or planned conditions. This definition shows that concerns for Manpower planning imply a future direction and as such the substance of it is to get ready for and foresee occasions.

Due to steady changes in the climate, persistent Manpower planning is a fundamental change that faces managers to design trying to uncover ahead of time openings for, and dangers to the program. By and large, achievement or disappointment relies upon an ability to adjust to design both to new data and changing natural conditions. In this way, Manpower planning is an interaction by which managers use and decide future activity that will prompt acknowledgment of wanted target. Manpower planning additionally assists with expecting future circumstances or conditions and their probable results. As such it empowers an association to accommodate method for accepting future vulnerabilities or if nothing else enhances their antagonistic effects. According to Agbato (1988), Manpower planning is the work to prepare faculty, envision the future, as history by deciding how we need the future to show up.

Manpower planning isn't the manner by which definitively we can foresee the future, but instead to uncover the things we should do today to have a future. This infers that Manpower planning includes gauging. Practically all Manpower planning include gauging and directors rely on these estimates in deciding reason for activity.

Onoha (1999), for labor wanting to be powerful, it should incorporate the accompanying standards; Manpower planning ought to be founded on unmistakably characterized objective and utilize all accessible

data. Manpower planning ought to consider factors in the climate which will help or upset the association in arriving at its objectives.

They should assess the current association and accommodate control, so execution can be checked with set up guidelines. They ought to be exact, practicable and easy to comprehend and work. They ought to be adaptable, to guarantee that conditions require change and this can be affected without disturbing the labor plan. Subsequently, Manpower planning regardless of by whatever it is characterized, has one essential point and that is the achievement of individual and friends targets.

1.3 Manpower planning problems

Individuals think that the human resource planning is not necessary and time consuming. Work force can be masterminded whenever at the time of necessity, with alluring advantages and motivations so why human resource planning. They think it is a simple task to control the work force in the organization. In this competitive business world it is extremely troublesome and challenging to compete with the opponents without defining appropriate key planning. Many have the insight that individuals who formulate the human resource plan are not expert in business, because of which they may commit mistake while formulating the human resource plan. A strategic plan is set for accomplishing the goals and objectives of the organization. At the time of detailing of technique the pre-owned data is fundamentally long term oriented. However, the human resource planning is formulated for utilizing the transient data. So the data of human asset doesn't regularly coordinate with the data of strategy formulation.

Human resource planning needs full and wholehearted help from the top management. Without this support and responsibility, it would not be feasible to ensure the fundamental assets, collaboration and leading for the achievement of the human resource planning. Labor absenteeism, work turnover, trade cycles, innovative changes and market variances are the vulnerabilities which fill in as imperatives to Human Resources planning. It is unsafe to rely on broad evaluations of human resource notwithstanding fast changes in environment.

1.4 Rational of the study

The present study is significant from various points of view:

As industries and technologies evolve, new generation enters as the workforce, and globalization creates increased competition, it will be the human resource issues that make or break a company. Only a significant research has been done on the manufacturing industry and a lot is required to be done of the manufacturing industry. Therefore we have chosen the manufacturing industry. The manufacturing area has contributed little to economic growth and its offer in all out product trades has been declining. Manufacturing has not brought a lot of new business, and the greater part of the ongoing ascent in manufacturing employment has been in the casual area, where laborers are not covered by government backed retirement plans. Efficiency of the manufacturing area is low, incompletely on the grounds that the generally little size of manufacturing firms makes it hard to misuse economies of scale. Notwithstanding bountiful, low-talented and generally modest work, Indian manufacturing is shockingly capital and ability escalated. Moreover, firms have minimal motivating force to develop, since by remaining little they can evade charges and complex work guidelines. Land procurement is moderate, organizations face regular force

blackouts and transport foundation is worse than average. This is particularly hurtful as manufacturing is exceptionally dependent on well-working foundation. More grounded assembling would build efficiency and make development more comprehensive, while adding to improved current record balance. Specifically, India should focus on more conventional positions, as these will in general be the most secure and of most noteworthy profitability.

This research is primarily focuses on the following objectives:

- ❖ To know the factors affecting the performance of an employees at workplace.
- ❖ To determine the relationship between physical components at work and performance.
- ❖ To determine the relationship between behavioural components at work and performance.

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Manpower planning is the way toward assessing the ideal number of individuals needed for finishing a task, goal or an objective within time. Manpower planning incorporates boundaries like number of faculty, various sorts of abilities, time span and so forth .It is a ceaseless nonstop cycle to ensure that the business has the upgraded resources accessible when required thinking about the impending future ventures and furthermore the substitution of the active employees. It is also called as Human Resource Planning.

This study decides the degree of performance among the employees who are working in the manufacturing industry and the degree of fulfillment of the employee satisfaction in the manufacturing industry. This thus decides the presentation through which the ideal usage of the enlisted faculty should be possible to nullify the excess and repetitive posts as this straightforwardly influences the expense and the general targets of the organization.

1.6 HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

H1: There exists a significant relationship between physical components at work and productivity of employees.

H2: There exists a significant a relationship between behavioral components at work and productivity of employees.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Agu (2003), Manpower planning and development gives the organization an internal compass and reason. In this manner, the steady aides required in resource designations are utilized in performing different exercises are given. It builds the aptitude of a supervisor in exact dynamic and accordingly lessens the odds of mix-ups and blunders. It likewise lessens misuse of materials, time and money.

According to Obi (2005), manpower planning and development is utilized to envision issues and make remedial move before they become danger to the association tasks and to co-ordinate every huge action with the goal that faculty, offices and materials can be made accessible at required time.

Drucker (1954) characterizes it as methods for utilizing subordinates. It is a means of using goals to motivate people rather than to control them.

Noe et al (2003) explained that it is imperative to properly actualize human resource planning so as to make the lead time important to face expected issues and dangers to the association's serious edge.

Byers and Rue, (1984) human resource planning includes applying the essential arranging cycle to human asset needs of the association. To be powerful, any human asset plan must be gotten from the long haul and activity plans of the association.

Walker(1990)Basically, the accomplishment of the human resource planning relies generally upon how intently the human asset division can incorporate viable individuals arranging with organization's business arranging measure.

Michael (2006) has indicated that the human resource happens inside the setting of the association. The degree to which it is utilized, and the methodology embraced, will be dependent upon the degree to which the board perceives that achievement relies upon anticipating future individuals prerequisite and actualizing plan to fulfill those necessity.

2.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1 Kind of Research:

This research is about to know the effect of manpower planning on employees performance who are working in manufacturing industries. For our research we have chosen the medical device manufacturing industries of DELHI/NCR. SPSS will be used as a tool to analyze the data collected for the research after checking the reliability and validity of the data collected. The chi-square test, correlation and multiple regressions will be used to analyze the data collected in order to satisfy the objectives defined in this study.

2.2 Variables:

There are two variables of our study: (a) physical components (b) behavioral components

2.3 Target Population:

Our research targeted the managerial and non-managerial personnel are who are currently working in medical device manufacturing industries of DELHI/NCR.

2.4 Method of Data Collection:

Data collection is an important part of the methodology. For our research we had collected the data through questionnaires. In order to quantify the conclusion of the research we have designed the open ended and close ended questions. Two separate questionnaires were prepared for both the personnel's (a) managerial personnel (b) non-managerial personnel. The questionnaires contained the questions related to the physical components and behavioral components like - furniture and furnishing at workplace, spatial

The Effect of Manpower Planning on the Performance...

arrangements at workplace, room temperature , lightening , noise free environment, interpersonal relations , emotional factors , job assignments , over time duty , extended duty.

(A) Questionnaire I – Managerial personnel

(B) Questionnaire II- Non-managerial personnel

2.5 Sample Size:

Total sample size of our research has been drawn for our study is 550. Out of which the 504 were the employees from non-managerial level and 46 were from the managerial level.

2.6 Demographic profile of the respondents

1. Gender of the respondents.

Table 2.6.1: Gender of the respondents

	Managers		Non-Managers	
	Number of respondents	percentage	Number of respondents	percentage
Male	35	76	485	96
Female	11	24	19	4

The majority of the respondents were male (table 4.1). 76% of the managers were male respondents and 24% were female. In case of non-managers 96% were male and 4% were female.

2. Age

Table2.6.2: Age of the respondents

	Managers		Non-managers	
	Number of respondents	percentage	Number of respondents	percentage
20-30	1	2	118	23
30-40	17	37	142	28
40-50	15	33	130	26
50 and above	13	28	114	23

In case of managers 33% of the respondents were of the age group between 40 to 50 years and 28% were from the age group of 50 and above. In case of the non-managers 28% were from the age group between 30-40 and 26% were from the age group between 40-50. 23% of the respondents each were from the age group of 20-30 years and 50 and above.

3. Tenure

Table 2.6.3: Tenure of the respondents

	Number of respondents	percentage	Number of respondents	percentage
less than 6 months	0	0	116	23
6 months - 2 years	8	17	134	27
2-5 years	18	39	151	30
5-10 years	12	26	103	20
10 years and above	8	17	0	0

In the case of managers 39% of the respondents have been working with the organization for 2-5 years and 26% have been working for 5-10 years. For the non-managers 30% have been with the organization for 2-5 years and 27% have been working for 6 months to 2 years.

4. Work according to qualifications

Table 2.6.4: Work according to qualifications

	percentage	Number of respondents
Strongly disagree	0	0
Disagree	3	7
Neutral	22	48
Strongly agree	21	46
Agree	0	0

The Effect of Manpower Planning on the Performance...

Work according to qualifications

The graph shows the responses that whether the work which has been assigned to the managers is as per their qualifications. 46% of the respondents strongly agree to the statement but 48% of the respondents have given neutral response. Thus it may be inferred that probably the managers are not able to align their qualifications with the responsibilities assigned or they have not been oriented properly by the organization on their job roles matching with their qualifications.

5. Work according to skills

Table 2.6.5: work according to skills

	percentage	Number of respondents
Strongly Disagree	0	0
Disagree	0	0
Neutral	30	65
Strongly Agree	16	35
Agree	0	0

Work according to skills

The graph shows the responses that whether the work which has been assigned to the managers is as per their skills. 35% of the respondents strongly agree to the statement but 65% of the respondents have given neutral response. Thus it may be inferred that probably the managers are not able to align their skills with the responsibilities assigned or they have not been oriented properly by the organization on their job roles matching with their skills.

3.0 Relationship between Physical Components at Work and Performance

Table3.1: Chi-Square Test of Physical components at work and productivity of the employees

Physical components	Chi-square value	df	Significance
Furniture and furnishings	2.601	3	0.457
Spatial arrangement	1.167	2	0.558
Temperature	2.546	3	0.467
Lighting	4.278	3	0.233
Noise	6.415	2	0.40

In the above table, it is observed that all the values of chi-square test are less than the table value. The table value at df 3 is 12.838 and df 2 is 10.597. The chi-square value seen above is less than the table value, so the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Moreover in all the cases the level of significance is greater than 0.005. So, **the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternate hypothesis is rejected**. Hence, we may infer that there does not exist any relationship between the physical components and the productivity of the employees.

Relationship between behavioral components at work and performance

Table3.2: Chi-Square Test of Behavioral components at work and productivity of the employees

Interpersonal relation	Chi-square value	df	Significance
Emotions	0.225	1	0.635
Spatial arrangement	0.167	2	0.920
Job Assignment	0.001	1	0.979
Overtime duty	0.795	2	0.672
Extended work	1.479	2	0.477

In the above table, it is observed that all the values of chi-square test are less than the table value. The table value at df 3 is 12.838 and df 2 is 10.597. The chi-square value seen above is less than the table value, so the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Moreover in all the cases the level of significance is greater than 0.005. So, **the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternate hypothesis is rejected.** Hence, we may infer that there does not exist any relationship between the behavioral components and the productivity of the employees.

Factors affecting the performance of employees at workplace

Top 5 factors that affects the performance of an employees at workplace:

- 1. Management styles:** Effective management further develops inspiration, commitment, and execution. Helpless administration has the contrary impact - diminishing fulfilment, efficiency, and performance. One method for further developing execution, consequently, is to recognize and fix issues in administration.

Worker reviews can offer speedy understanding into the condition of the board inside an organization, pinpoint likely issues, then, at that point, recommend roads for fixing those issues.
- 2. Corporate Culture:**organizational culture is made out of convictions and presumptions that, to a limited extent, drive representative conduct. Certain characteristics and practices emphatically affect specialist execution, while others have an adverse consequence. For example, these characteristics can assist with further developing labour force execution: A culture worked around constant learning and improvement

A faith in the worth of computerized proficiency and advanced finesse Receptiveness to change and novel thoughts There is no single characteristic or thought that can change representative conduct for the time being - truth be told, social changes are troublesome and set aside time. In any case, instilling the right qualities into a working environment can assist with changing the manner in which representatives contemplate work and, all the more significantly, how they perform.
- 3. Digital work environment:** The computerized work environment incorporates: The computerized devices representatives use how those computerized devices are utilized computerized preparing and abilities improvement Computerized work processes. The computerized workplace can be liquid, consistent, and easy to understand. Or then again it very well may be divided and incoherent. The in excess of an association puts resources into its computerized part, the more joyful representatives will be, and the better they will perform.

4. **Physical work environment:** The actual workplace likewise influences significant worker measurements, like commitment, fulfilment, and execution. Great workplaces ought to be custom fitted to the requirements of the work environment culture and the labour force. High speed innovative new companies, for example, will quite often establish workplaces that mirror their way of life, their qualities, and their central goal. Many incorporate animating stylistic layout, action regions, games, etc. A similar workplace would not work, notwithstanding, for an organization with an alternate culture in an alternate industry.

Nonetheless, paying little mind to industry or culture, the actual climate assumes a part in presentation. For the most part, the better the workplace – from work areas to style – the better representatives will feel at their particular employment.

5. **Employees experience :** The employees experience incorporates each phase of the worker venture, including:
- Recruiting
 - On boarding
 - Commitment
 - Post-Exit Interactions

That experience relies upon its own arrangement of elements, some of which are shrouded in this rundown. Making a positive employee's encounter offers various advantages:

- Better execution
- More representative commitment and inspiration
- Expanded commitment
- Less contact

Today, many organizations understand that the representative experience isn't simply "what tops off an already good thing" – it assumes an immediate part in how much worth workers add to the association.

Expected Outcomes

- This type of study is not available on medical devices on which our study focuses.
- Research plans to fill the gaps recognized and adds to analytical insights of knowledge on explicit factors and their inter-linkages.

CONCLUSION

The organization should take special steps to improve the physical ambience emphasising on adequate workspace, proper lighting and noise management. Moreover, the findings also reveal that physical components and behavioural components do not have any relationship with performance of the employees. Organizations make ventures for laborers' training and development to construct their level of capacities and productivity. In a discussion about work power masterminding, when delegates are outfitted with

express preparing about their work and occupation, they can perform better and carefully whether or not there is no administration in the wake of preparing occurs. Engaged representatives accordingly, have significant levels of vitality and are energetic about their work. Job satisfaction was perceived as one's disposition towards his/her work. At the end of the day work fulfillment mirrored an individual's passionate reaction towards the different occupation aspects. An individual who was profoundly happy with his work hold the uplifting mentality towards his work, while the one who had significant degree of occupation disappointment hold the negative demeanor towards the work. In case of the physical components, the chi-square value is less than the table value, so the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Moreover in all the cases the level of significance is greater than 0.005. So, the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternate hypothesis is rejected. Hence, we may infer that there does not exist any relationship between the physical components and the productivity of the employees. In case of the behavioural components the chi-square value is less than the table value, so the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Moreover in all the cases the level of significance is greater than 0.005. So, the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternate hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it can be inferred that there does not exist any relationship between the behavioural components and the productivity of the employees.

REFERENCES

Murgai,A.(2018).Role of artificial intelligence in transforming human resource management. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Dvelopment*,2(3),877.

Pandey,S.Khaskel,P.(2019).Application of AI in human resource management Gen Y's Reaction. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, 8(4), 2277-3878.

Rani,S.(2019).Human resource management and artificial intelligence. *International Research Journal of Management Sociology & Humanities*, 10(7), 2277-9809.

WHO, 2010.*Medical Devices: Managing the Mismatch*, Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization Press.

George,V.(2019).The role of human resource planning in the human resource network. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 2320-2882.

Sreekumar,M.Chhabra,M.Yadav,R.(2018).Productivity in manufacturing industries.*International Journal Of Innovative Science and Research Technology*. 3(10),2456-2165.

Feuer, M.J., Niehaus, R.J. & Sheridan, J.A. (1984). Human resource planning: A survey of practice and potential. *Human Resource Planning*. 7, 85-97.

Gomathi,S.(2020).Impact of employee motivation on productivity at manufacturing private sector.

International Journal Of Economic and Business Review-Peer Reviewed Journal,8(5),2347-9671.

Nda,M.Fard,R.(2013). The impact of employee training and development on employee productivity.*Global Journal of Commerce and Management Perspective*,2(6),91-93.

Ofotokun,O.S.(2012).The role of manpower planning in organizational behavior. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Empirical Research*,10(1).

Salah,M.(2016).The impact of training and development on employees performance and productivity. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*,5(7),2226-8235.

Anvadike.(2013).Human resource planning and productivity in Nigeria public organization. *Global Journal Of Human Resource Management*,1(4),56-68.

Onyebuchi,O.(2017).Impact of manpower training and development on organizational productivity and performance A theoretical review. *European Journal of Business and Management*,9(4),2222-1905.

Mbui,A.(2018).Influence of Human resource planning on employee productivity in county governments in Kenya. *Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*,5(4),193-214.

Shankari,S.(2017).Literature review on evaluation and impact of human resource management on enterprise performance management in the manufacturing industry. *International Journal of Current Engineering and Scientific Research*,4(8),2393-8374.

Srinivasan,K.(2014).Impact of trends in Indian pharmaceutical industry on training and development practices and birth of innovative approaches. *International Journal of Management and Social Science Research review*,1(2),2349-6738.